

A system for objectively measuring behavior and the environment to support large-scale studies on childhood obesity

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Abstract

Advances in IoT technologies combined with new algorithms have enabled the collection and processing of high-rate multi-source data streams that quantify human behavior in a fine-grained level and can lead to deeper insights on individual behaviors as well as on the interplay between behaviors and the environment. In this paper, we present an integrated system that collects and extracts multiple behavioral and environmental indicators, aiming at improving public health policies for tackling obesity. Data collection takes place using passive methods based on smartphone and smartwatch applications that require minimal interaction with the user. Our goal is to present a detailed account of the design principles, the implementation processes, and the evaluation of integrated algorithms, especially given the challenges we faced, in particular (a) integrating multiple technologies, algorithms, and components under a single, unified system, and (b) large scale (big data) requirements. We also present evaluation results of the algorithms on datasets (public for most cases) such as an absolute error of 8-9 steps when counting steps, 0.86 F1-score for detecting visited locations, and an error of less than 12 mins for gross sleep time. Finally, we also briefly present studies that have been materialized using our system, thus demonstrating its potential value to public authorities and individual researchers.

Tags: Behavior Monitoring, Behavioral Studies, Health Informatics, Machine Learning, Obesity, Public Health, Wearable Health Monitoring, Big Data, Real-World Data

1 Introduction

Obesity is recognized as a major public health challenge worldwide and its prevalence has been rising since 1975 [1]. It affects both physical and mental health and is linked with a range of comorbidities with negative health outcomes. It is also a disease that is costly, severely impacting healthcare systems throughout the world [2].

At the policy level, addressing obesity has proven to be challenging since its complexity [3] implies that single-

element, blanket interventions are ineffective [4]. Many experts now agree that targeted, multi-factorial interventions are needed instead [5]. Furthermore, prevention of obesity is easier than treatment, and therefore interventions aiming at preventing obesity for children and adolescents are a priority [6].

Design of such multi-level interventions at a population level requires detailed information about the behavior of age subgroups (children, adolescents, etc.), as well as about the presence of obesogenic factors in their environment. Passive collection of behavioral information through smartphones and smartwatches (based on the sensors commonly embedded on such devices) is an appealing alternative to questionnaire-based research since it is (i) scalable, with volunteers using their own devices for data collection, (ii) detailed, since information is collected continuously and with high frequency, and (iii) objective, as behavioral information is quantified by algorithms based on sensor signals. Furthermore, collection of environmental obesogenic factors can also be facilitated by taking advantage of highly-detailed public repositories of census data, public maps, etc. combined with novel, state-of-the-art algorithms to extract obesity-related factors. Some examples of our earlier work on these topics can be found in [7] and [8].

To implement this approach, several technical challenges need to be addressed. These include selecting suitable raw data types, extracting useful and meaningful indicators accurately and/or with minimal error, handling missing data and data quality issues, handling big data processing requirements, as well as issues related to privacy protection. It is worth noting that most of these challenges are not specific to obesity; they apply to most systems that perform large-scale collection of behavioral and environmental data and indicators.

In this paper, we present the architecture of a system that enables both passive and active collection of behavior and environment data at large scale. The proposed system was originally designed and implemented in the context of the EU-funded project BigO [9,10] to support acquisition of behavioral data from over 4,000 children and adolescents in four European countries. We discuss key require-

ments and design choices that benefit any similar systems, the system architecture, along with implementation and deployment details, extending our previous work of [11] where we present and evaluate algorithms that are used in the system and extract behavioral indicators. Furthermore, we briefly outline examples of usage of this system in the school and clinical setting as well as the value of this approach for use in official statistics.

While the proposed system heavily relies on existing technologies and algorithms, there are some important challenges (relevant to) that it must overcome:

1. There is no predetermined set of capturing apparatus. Instead, any smartphone and Android smart-watch can contribute data. This introduces multiple challenges both in creating a robust data-capturing application that handles all idiosyncrasies of each operating system and device vendor, as well as in designing and implementing pre-processing steps that curate and standardize all collected signals.
2. Real-world data collection happens outside of controlled experimental environments without any standardized protocol or script, introducing missing data, data with limited duration or sparse over a time-span.
3. While the application of algorithms that extract indicators is a central part of the system, additional algorithms are needed for aggregation and privacy-preserving purposes.
4. Aligning and combining data from different sources (such as individual behavioral indicators and environmental indicators) is a necessary, non-trivial task, requiring both spatial and temporal processing.

All these challenges create a complex system that goes way beyond the application and evaluation of individually developed algorithms under controlled data-collection trials. The result is a single, integrated system that can handle large volumes of data, enabling users such as public-health authorities and individual researchers to understand obesity and its factors, and to eventually design effective policies and solutions against obesity.

The following Section discusses relevant literature, while Section 3 outlines the system architecture at component level. Section 4 describes the data-acquisition tools and methods, the indicator extraction algorithms, the types of indicators, and the types of analyses. Section 5 presents examples of the evaluation methodology along with results for various indicator-extraction components. Section 6 presents examples of real-world uses of the system. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 Related work

Using big data in the context of obesity is generally considered to have significant potential in facilitating research on multiple obesity-related risk factors and their combinations [12]. A recent Delphi study has aggregated views of experts on the use of big data to tackle obesity [13]. The study concluded that there is a need to develop (and also

encourage the adoption of) tools for reporting, ethics, data governance, and sharing of data. Another Delphi study, carried in the context of the BigO project [14], shows that there is consensus among policy makers on measuring and monitoring built, dietary and social environment indicators with respect to obesity prevention.

In [15], authors present an analysis of physical activity estimation using a commercial application for smartphones in interactions with socio-demographics. Among the main findings is that smartphone ownership (and thus, the ability to collect big behavioral data) is not a limiting factor for reaching lower socioeconomic groups.

Three different case studies are summarized in [16] where big data have been used in obesity research. In these studies, big data have been used to associate (a) physical activity with green spaces and exercise facilities, (b) obesity surgery and the risk of developing cancer, and (c) various socio-demographic parameters of the Seattle area in the USA, with obesity.

Crowd-sourced data from GPS-enabled smartphones, specifically from Strava Metro [17], were collected during 2013-2014 in Queensland, Australia [18], and analyzed offline. The data are used to evaluate the impact of changes in infrastructure on cycling behavior. Authors state that the “passive” method they use to collect data leads to higher volume and more accurate analysis compared to recruitment or questionnaire-based studies.

Similarly, in [19] authors perform an analysis of trajectories of cyclists and produced heat-maps that can be used in applications such as city planning. Data were collected from the city of Helsinki. Authors have considered privacy and introduce k -anonymity to the analysis results (where both the density of trajectories and users are taken into account).

The DAPHNE project [20] is an EU-funded study that collected data from an activity sensor, offering cloud-based data-analysis services. The goal of the project is to reduce sedentary behavior, especially in the context of obesity.

Finally, in [21], the Raine Study studies behaviors and the environment, as well as genetics to understand social outcomes and to improve health and well-being.

The presented architecture and system takes into consideration the findings of these previous studies and provides implementation details for a system that can be deployed on user-owned smartphones to facilitate data collection and decision-support. While we tailor the system to the BigO project requirements for obesity prevention at the policy level, we follow a generalizable methodology suitable to any kind of behavior-monitoring system.

3 System architecture

3.1 Design considerations

The main objective of any such a system is to characterize population behavior and environmental factors for each geographic segment and monitor population-behavior changes over time as the result of policy interventions. This is a three-step process: define the geographic segments, extract population behavior, and extract environ-

Figure 1: Generic architecture of the proposed system

mental factors. The design of such a system has to take into account the following requirements and considerations:

1. ability to collect, store, and efficiently retrieve large volumes of high-rate data (multiple samples of multi-channel signals) from user smartphones to the system server(s)
2. ability to collect and cache environmental and census data from public repositories
3. ability to extract behavioral information from the collected signals
4. ability to aggregate, summarize, and combine the computed behavioral information with the environmental data and present informative views

Based on these requirements, a generic system architecture is shown in Figure 1.

While the above requirements can be implemented in multiple ways, the following limitations should be taken into account:

1. The smartphone and wearable apps should have minimal impact on battery.
2. The volume of data transmitted between the devices and uploaded to the server should be minimal (for reducing the impact on both battery drain and bandwidth use).
3. Metadata should also be collected and used to support the detection of missing data (vs. periods of inactivity), to determine appropriate imputation methods, and to create logs and statistics.
4. Indicator extraction algorithms should be efficient, effective, and robust.
5. Population-level aggregations should be privacy preserving, i.e., they should not reveal information for specific individuals.

3.2 Design process

Several rounds of interviews and discussions with school personnel, clinicians, public-health representatives and childhood-obesity experts led to a set of key requirements for the proposed system [22]. These include both functional requirements related to the types of measurements recorded by the system, as well as non-functional requirements related to user privacy.

The users of the system are: (a) participating children and their teachers, to support educational activities on obesity prevention, (b) clinicians, who use aggregated measurements of their patient behavior to offer personalized consultation, and (c) public-health policy makers, who view measurements of population behavior and their environment as evidence to support policy decisions and monitor changes to evaluate the effectiveness of applied forces.

Behavioral data are primarily collected by the participants through their smartphone and smartwatch accelerometer and GPS sensors. Pictures are also contributed to self-report meals and food advertisements. In this context, the proposed system facilitates a participatory-sensing approach by enabling children and adolescents to provide data that help to better understand the local obesogenic environment. Environmental data is collected from publicly available repositories, including statistical authorities, census data sources, and public maps.

The collected data is processed at three layers (Figure 2).

The first layer is responsible for (a) data acquisition from smartphone and smartwatch sensors and external sources, and (b) extracting behavioral indicators (i.e., well-defined and quantifiable pieces of information) at a high temporal granularity (e.g., one value per minute).

At the second layer, behavior indicators such as “number of steps” and “visits to fast-food restaurant” are aggregated (across time) at two levels: (a) at the level of an individual, to summarize his/her behavior, and (b) at the level of geofencing (i.e., geographic segments), to summarize behavior that is exhibited within the limits of predefined geographical borders, typically covering the area of a neighborhood.

Finally, in the third layer, data are aggregated across the population, separately for each of the individual-based and geofence-based aggregations of the previous layer. This information is used for statistical analysis and to produce descriptive statistics, summary views, and choropleth maps.

To support these functionalities and satisfy the requirements and considerations of Section 3.1, the system is designed as shown in the UML component diagram (Figure 3).

The smartphone and Android-Wear smartwatch apps are designed with separate user interface (UI) and data-acquisition components, while the smartphone app also includes components for synchronization with the Android wear app, a local (to the smartphone) database for storing the collected data, metadata, and other diagnostic information, along with a server-uploading component. The

Figure 2: Data aggregation: from raw data to population-level behavioral indicators

Web Portals are independent web applications which also communicate with external map services.

Both the smartphone app and the web portals communicate with the server-side modules only through dedicated controller components (the mobile app controller and the portals controller, Figure 3), and a single authentication server is used to control access.

The server-side modules are organized in three groups. The database management system (DBMS) group is responsible for storing the high volumes of raw data that are collected by the smartphone app as well as communicating with external sources of environmental data (i.e., publicly available maps, census data, and demographic data sources). The analysis back-end modules process the collected data into meaningful behavioral and environmental indicators and perform aggregations. Finally, the analysis services implement the functionalities required for the web portals.

4 Information processing layers

4.1 Extracting population behavior

Extracting population behavior measurements requires computation of multiple behavioral indicators from the signals collected by the smartphone and smartwatch. We identify three main groups of such indicators: physical activity, location and transportation, and sleep.

Physical activity – We compute activity counts, steps, activity level (i.e., sedentary, moderate, vigorous, and very vigorous), and activity type (e.g., standing, walking, running) at regular intervals (i.e., once per minute). The input to all physical-activity algorithms presented in this section is the 3-dimensional (3D) accelerometer signal, at a relatively low sampling rate (usually in the range

of 5 to 25 Hz, depending on the device).

It should be noted that modern Android devices that are supported by our system offer different levels of sampling rates (“slow” [23], “medium” [24], “fast” [25], and “maximum” [26]), however these correspond to sampling rates that vary between different vendors and devices (i.e., smartphones and smartwatches). Initially, we developed part of the system using the “medium” sampling rates, which usually correspond to values around 50 Hz. However, this caused significant battery drain and the first users of the system had multiple complaints regarding this issue, leading to low user acceptance. Thus, we switched to the “slow” sampling rate (which is between 5 to 25 Hz) and adjusted our algorithms accordingly. While this choice did reduce the quality of extracted indicators, it was necessary to maintain an acceptable user experience.

Activity counts are commonly used in the physical-activity literature and are typically computed by devices manufactured by Actigraph [27]. These devices have been used extensively both in sleep-related [28] and physical activity-related studies [29].

Counting steps during walking is one of the most common indicators measured by many devices, i.e., fitness trackers (by companies like Fitbit or Garmin), smartwatches (Apple watch, Android smartwatches, etc.), and even smartphones. In most cases, proprietary algorithms and methods are used to estimate the number of walked steps, and sometimes these methods are integrated into the hardware, and are provided as “pedometer” sensors. To avoid discrepancies and differences between different software and hardware, two state-of-the-art algorithms are implemented in BigO, in particular the algorithms of [30] and [31]. The algorithm [30] is used on smartphone devices and is reported to achieve an error of 1% on free walking and 11.67% false walking on a dataset of eight volunteers performing 300 steps each on two trials (ground truth was created by volunteers actively counting their steps as they walked). The algorithm of [31] is used on smartwatch devices; it achieves a relative error of 1% to 3% on a dataset of eight people repeating 80 trials (ground truth was created by an external observer who counted the steps). Different algorithms are used for the two types of devices since the nature of the captured acceleration signals are different in each case. In particular, the algorithm of [30] mainly focuses on cases where the accelerometer is in the subject’s pocket or back-pack while the algorithm of [31] specifically focuses on smartwatches. Using the appropriate algorithm for each device type helps increase the effectiveness and reduce the overall absolute error between the detected and actual (ground truth) steps.

Detecting activity type involves processing the accelerometer signal to determine which activity the user is performing, from a predefined list of activity types. Detection is achieved using a machine-learning model, built for example using support vector machines (SVM), which can be trained on datasets with a predefined set of target classes. Common activity types include sitting, standing, walking, jogging, running, ascending stairs, and descending stairs; sometimes more fine-grained types are included, such as dish washing, vacuum cleaning, playing football,

Figure 3: UML Component diagram of the proposed system architecture.

playing basketball, etc.

The approach of [32] has been implemented for activity-type recognition, with some important differences between the application of the algorithm in the original paper and in BigO. These are:

- Accelerometer is sampled at a higher rate in [32]
- Multiple accelerometers are used simultaneously in [32] (their windows are synchronized in time and their feature vectors are concatenated); in our work, we only use one stream
- A heart-rate sensor is also used in [32]; in our work, we do not use the heart-rate sensor for physical activity

The limitations applied in BigO reduce the effectiveness of the algorithm, however the reduction is small (see Section 5) while it enables the practical application of the algorithm, i.e., does not require a user to wear a smartwatch on each hand, or for the smartphone to be strapped on belt, and does not require a constant heart-rate unit.

Location and transportation – Indicators related to location and transportation are computed on an event-based scale (i.e., they depend on when an individual arrives and departs from a specific location). In particular, we identify visited points-of-interest (including restaurants, gyms, parks, supermarkets, etc.), some locations with special significance (home and school), and also when and how the user moves from each location to another, i.e. transportation mode (e.g. walking, bicycling, using a bus). The input to all algorithms in this section is a sequence

Figure 4: Point-of-interest detection example with development data. Map data from Open Street Map.

of time-stamped location coordinates (latitude and longitude). Additionally, the transportation-mode detection algorithm also uses the acceleration signal (this is the same signal that is used for extracting the physical-activity indicators). Figure 4 illustrates examples of detected POIs and transportation mode, using publicly available datasets and development data collected within BigO.

To detect POIs, we follow the approach of [33] that detects visited locations from a set of recorded coordinates (called location points from now on). The algorithm introduces a metric called move-ability and computes a density value that is used by a modified version of the DBSCAN algorithm.

Home and school detection relies on detecting the most frequently-visited POIs. We apply heuristic rules that take into account frequency, time of day, and weekday, and

recognize which PoI is the user’s home and which one is their school.

Note that once the type (e.g., park, restaurant) of a visited PoI has been determined, the actual coordinates of the visited PoI are deleted. This is done for data minimization and privacy protection purposes.

Detecting transportation mode requires detecting visited PoIs first, since a subject cannot be traveling while visiting a PoI. Thus, time intervals between PoIs can be examined as candidate “trips”. Once a time interval is identified as a trip, the corresponding accelerometer data is extracted and used to detect transportation mode based on the algorithm of [34]. The implementation of BigO has some minor differences from the algorithm as presented in [34], in particular:

- Use of smaller windows (1 sec instead of 10 sec) to allow more fine-grained detection
- Additional features (power spectral density)
- Different classifier (SVM instead of random forest)
- A post-processing median filter

Sleep – For estimating sleep behavior, we use the acceleration signal we collect from the smartwatch. While there are a lot of from dominant-hand worn sensors [35], in our case the smartwatch was usually worn on the wrist of the non-dominant hand. Although a lot of methods have been implemented recently for estimating sleep from raw accelerometer data, they are not drastically different from older methods, nor are they extensively evaluated [36–38]. On the other hand, initial methods based on activity counts have been tested in multiple scenarios both in research studies and in the industry. Among them, the most famous are [39] and [40]. These methods have been evaluated in a wide range of studies [38] and have demonstrated satisfactory results. For this reason, we choose these methods and adapt their implementation for our proposed system (i.e., using different sampling rates).

Both implementations are based on activity counts extracted from 1-minute windows; they output boolean predictions (sleeping vs. not-sleeping) for each 1-minute window. Based on these boolean labels, we compute six indicators: gross sleep time (GST), sleep start (SS), sleep end (SE), total time of interrupts (TTI), number of interrupts (NI), and net sleep time (NST).

4.2 Spatial aggregation

To enable the collection of behavioral information for locations without compromising the anonymity of the users, we employ a mechanism that aggregates behavior across spatial regions. This mechanism is based on the “geohash system” [41,42], which is a public-domain geocoding mechanism. The geohash system encodes GPS coordinates to short, alphanumerical strings; each string (a “geohash”) is a unique identifier for a rectangular geographic area. This is the main mechanism for encoding geographical regions in the proposed system.

An advantage of using geohashes is that it is possible to control the granularity of the area, simply by removing characters from the end of the geohash.

The ability to easily apply various levels of privacy protection regarding an individual’s location makes the geohash system appropriate for collecting spatial behavioral measurements. In BigO, this data collection is realized through the geohash votes mechanism, which operates as follows:

1. The system detects a visit of an individual inside a particular geohash
2. The system measures the individual’s behavior during the visit (details are provided in Section 4.1)
3. A anonymous vote is cast, indicating the behavior of one individual during his/her stay at that geohash

Given enough users and time, each geohash (within a study area, e.g., a city or municipality) is populated with many votes from multiple users. It is important to note that these votes are anonymous, i.e., they cannot be tracked back to the specific user who cast the vote (the system, however, does keep track of a mapping using anonymized IDs to avoid double voting). The votes of each geohash can then aggregated in many ways and summarize behavior of the population within very specific geographical limits.

Using the geohash-votes mechanism, we can collect aggregated information about the behavior of the population during their visits at particular locations, without the need to store individual location data centrally. An alternative (but similar) representation can result if individuals cast votes in fixed, regular time intervals (e.g., every quarter, or every hour). This option, however, can conceal the total visit time of a subject to a region (geohash).

4.2.1 Aggregation and data analysis

The behavioral indicators that are computed by the algorithms of Section 4.1 have high temporal resolution, and correspond to individual events (e.g., a visit to a restaurant, a morning walk to school) or to measurements with high sampling rate (e.g., activity type performed every minute). We call these “Base indicators”. The detailed information of base indicators cannot be easily visualized or communicated for the purposes of behavioral research, or to support policy decisions. Additionally, visualizing base behavioral indicators or using them directly for analysis may raise privacy concerns.

The proposed system therefore supports data aggregation functionalities that produce measurements summarizing individual or population behavior, as in [7]. Aggregation can take place at the individual and at the population level.

Individual-level aggregation – The supported aggregation functions include summation, averaging, and distribution estimation using histograms. Applying these aggregations to base indicators results in

- *Individual visitor indicators*: aggregation of individual behavior during the time spent at a specific region

(geohash). Examples include the average number of steps per hour during visits to the location, or the percentage of visits to the location that resulted in a visit to a cafe.

- *Individual resident indicators*: aggregation of individual behavior, irrespective of location. In this case indicators are computed by aggregating the overall behavior of individuals that reside in a specific geohash. Examples include the time spent performing the “running” activity per week, the distribution of monthly visits to a set of location types (e.g., gym, restaurant, park). “Behavior profiles” can be used as a formal way to describe an individual’s behavior and as input to machine learning and analysis algorithms [43]. A behavior profile first aggregates data of PoIs and transitions to generate a probabilistic mobility graph for each user. In addition, aggregated indicators are calculated for each node (i.e., PoI type), such as physical activity and time spent, and for each edge (i.e., transition), such as distance and transportation mode.

Note that spatial aggregation can be implemented in both cases. In the first case, the vote is cast to the visited geohash, while in the second case the vote is cast to the user’s resident geohash (even if the activity took place elsewhere).

One difficulty that occurs when applying aggregation functions is handling missing data. It is common to have periods with missing recordings for reasons that include (a) sensor or application failure, (b) the recording service being stopped by the smartphone operating system and (c) the user manually stopping data acquisition. The approach that we followed in this system implementation is to apply a filter to remove days with recording time below a threshold from the aggregation. Moreover, using normalized measures, such as average number of steps per hour instead of absolute number of steps can make indicators from users with different amount of data recordings comparable.

Population-level indicators – The next step is to aggregate individual-level measurements to produce population-level behavioral indicators. Given a neighborhood (defined as a geographical region) or geohash, we can again distinguish between *visitor* and *resident* indicators.

Visitor indicators summarize the behavior of individuals during their visit in the neighborhood. These can be computed directly by applying an aggregation function to the individual visitor indicators of the previous section. Resident indicators, on the other hand, summarize the behavior of individuals living in a particular neighborhood, irrespective of where their behavior took place. These can be computed by aggregating individual indicators.

Examples of visitor indicators include and “percentage of neighborhood visitors that performed at least 10 minutes of the running activity”, “average number of steps per hour of visitors” and “average time spent in restaurants per visitor”. Examples of resident indicators include the “daily average number of steps”, “number of weekly sessions of at least 20 minutes of walking” and “average number of weekly visits to restaurants”.

Furthermore, the geohash-votes mechanism has been used in combination with local environmental characteristics to produce machine learning models for estimating population behavior in new areas. This approach has demonstrated high predictive performance [44] and can be used for generalizing in areas without data (e.g., different parts of the same metropolitan area where population data are not available) or for imputation purposes when visualizing heatmaps (e.g., geohashes that happen to have no votes or very few votes that fall below the privacy thresholds).

To avoid introducing bias, only individuals with sufficient volume of data are considered in the computation of the population-level indicators.

4.3 Extracting environmental factors

While the chosen geographic segment (in the context of BigO) is the geohash, environmental information is usually available in different scales such as an administrative region. Given the focus of BigO on providing decision support for public health authorities, this information plays a central role for analysis.

The main driver for the selection of environmental factors to be modeled in BigO has been the available literature and the Delphi study [14]. In total, 46 factors were identified, in the following 5 categories:

1. *Urban environment* (20 factors), e.g., number of supermarkets and grocery stores, number of restaurants and food outlets
2. *School* (6 factors), e.g., school exercise programs, school meals/breaks
3. *Socioeconomic, pricing, and inequalities* (10 factors): e.g., average income in neighborhood, education-level statistics
4. *Food marketing* (3 factors), e.g., exposure to food advertisements from TV
5. *Policy* (7 factors), e.g., sugar tax, salt tax

Automatically extracted environmental factors result from information available through statistical authorities, GIS platforms etc. Others need to be manually measured and provided, such as the pricing of different types of goods.

Depending on the country or region, some of the factor values may not be available. In other cases, data is available but not at the required level of geographical detail. In these cases, one may use methodologies that consider surrogate variables, such as the one proposed in [8].

4.4 Final list of behavioral indicators

Based on the information extracted from the algorithms described so far, multiple population-behavior indicators can be computed, on different aggregation levels (both temporal and spatial). Table 1 presents the consolidated list of population-level behavioral indicators that we extract.

Table 1: List of aggregated behavioral indicators per spatial region

Indicator	Aggregation per			Sensor		
	<i>resident</i>	<i>visitor</i>	<i>vote</i>	<i>acc.</i>	<i>loc.</i>	<i>G.I.S.</i>
<i>Physical activity</i>						
Average:						
- activity counts/minute		✓	✓	✓		
- hourly steps		✓	✓	✓		
- daily steps	✓			✓		
- sedentary minutes after school	✓			✓	✓	
- sleep duration	✓			✓		
Distribution of physical activity:						
- types	✓			✓		
- levels		✓	✓	✓		
Percentage of individuals with:						
- sedentary-behavior		✓	✓	✓		
- sedentary average activity level	✓			✓		
- at least 60 min of average daily walking time	✓			✓		
<i>Visits</i>						
Percentage of votes with at least one visit to:						
- a food-related location			✓		✓	✓
- to supermarkets or grocery stores			✓		✓	✓
- a fast food or a takeaway restaurant			✓		✓	✓
- a public park			✓		✓	✓
- a recreational facility			✓		✓	✓
- an athletics or sports facility			✓		✓	✓
Average number of weekly visits to:						
- restaurants	✓				✓	✓
- food outlets	✓				✓	✓
- cafes	✓				✓	✓
- fast food locations	✓				✓	✓
- food-related locations	✓				✓	✓
- supermarkets or grocery stores	✓				✓	✓
- restaurants or food outlets	✓				✓	✓
- take-away restaurants	✓				✓	✓
- fast food or take-away restaurants	✓				✓	✓
- bars	✓				✓	✓
- wine or liquor stores	✓				✓	✓
- public parks	✓				✓	✓
Average number of visits to:						
- indoor recreational facilities	✓				✓	✓
- athletics or sports facilities	✓				✓	✓
<i>Mobility</i>						
Distribution of transportation modes	✓	✓	✓	✓		

5 Experiments & results with indicator extraction algorithms

This section presents the methodology for evaluating each indicator-extraction algorithm of the system. The experiments and results presented here are not exhaustive; they instead focus on some of the fundamental algorithms of the system (such as the step-counting algorithm or the sleep-detection algorithm) and present evaluation results on publicly available datasets. However, a similar methodology can be followed for each of the behavioral indicators presented in Table 1, given appropriate ground truth.

5.1 Physical activity

Step-counting is evaluated on the publicly-available dataset of [45]. It includes time-series recordings from 27 participants using smartphones; each participant performed 130 walks using six smartphone placements simultaneously with an average of 78 ± 8.34 steps per walk. The recordings were made without any constraints. The smartphones were placed at different positions, such as front or back trouser pocket, handbag, or were held by the participants. Additional datasets also exist [46, 47], however, they were published after the project’s main development period and thus they were not available for experimentation during that time.

The number of detected steps is validated against ground truth, and results are presented in Table 2. Ground truth number of steps, detected steps, absolute and relative errors are shown per device position. Overall absolute error is 8 steps (per recording), and overall relative error is 9.7%.

For evaluating physical activity type detection, the PAMAP2 dataset [32] is used. It includes 12 activity types, both basic every-day activities, postures, and motion types. Each participant performed all activities in a predefined order; each activity was performed for 3 minutes approximately (the only exceptions that lasted less being ascending and descending stairs and rope jumping). In total, 8 hours of data were collected.

5.2 Location and transportation

PoI detection and transportation mode recognition algorithms are evaluated on the Sussex-Huawei locomotion (SHL) dataset [48, 49]. The dataset was collected by the Wearable Technologies Lab at the University of Sussex as part of a research project funded by Huawei. It contains multiple modes of locomotion and transportation, as captured by various sensors (inertial, location, audio, and more) of smartphones. Currently, data from 3 participants are available, that include 3 days of recordings per participant.

Evaluation of PoI algorithm is performed on the SHL dataset, using the location data as input and the ground truth state to determine visited locations.

Classification results are computed by performing a “matching” process between ground-truth and detected PoIs. This process is described by the following rules

- Each ground-truth PoI can be matched with at most one detected PoI
- Each detected PoI can be matched with at most one ground-truth PoI
- Matching requires a maximum of distance between ground-truth and detected center co-ordinates
- Matching requires a minimum of overlap in time between ground-truth and detected PoIs

Each pair of matched ground-truth and detected PoIs is counted as 1 true positive (TP) detection. Each non-matched ground-truth PoI is counted as 1 false negative (FN) detection. Finally, each non-matched detected PoI is counted as 1 false positive (FP) detection.

Table 4 presents the classification results. All TP, FP, and FN are shown for each subject, as well as three additional metrics: precision, recall, and F1-score. Additionally, total results are shown in the last line of the results Table. Total results are computed by summing TP, FP, and FN from all subjects in order to obtain TP, FP, and FN for the entire dataset, and the remaining metrics are computed on the basis of the entire dataset TP, FP, and FN.

Detection of transportation mode is evaluated on the SHL dataset. The leave-one-subject-out scheme was used to train and test the classification models on the three users of the dataset.

The different transportation modes that are available are walk/run, bike, car, bus, and train/subway. In total, 7 modes were merged into 5 due to similarities between train and subway in one case, and walking and running in the other case (walking can be differentiated from running by the activity type detection algorithm). The number of data points per class were not equal in the dataset, so class weights were used during model training. Class weights were chosen as $w_i = \min_k n_k / n_i$, $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ where n_i is the number of data points of the i -th class that are available during training. Additionally, C parameter was set equal to 1000, while the radial-basis-function kernel was used with parameter $\gamma = 1/D$ where D is the number of features (feature-vector dimension).

5.3 Sleep

Two datasets are being used for evaluating the performance of the sleep detection methods. Newcastle dataset [37] which is publicly available and a dataset we created on our own (BigO dataset). It should be noted that both datasets contain recordings only from adults, as it was not possible to obtain recordings from children (i.e., the BigO’s target population) with ground truth.

Newcastle dataset, provided by [37], is the only publicly available dataset that combines raw accelerometer data and ground truth labeling from polysomnography test. The study took place in Newcastle upon Tyne (UK) in 2015. The data comes from a single night recording of 28 sleep clinic patients. The majority of them are aged over 50 years old and face serious sleep disorders, which makes them unsuitable for validating our algorithms. For

Table 2: Evaluation results (average error and std) of step calculation for the different phone placements of the dataset of [45] for the algorithm of [30]

Position	#	Predicted steps	Absolute error	Relative error (%)
Hand-held	21	73 ± 16	8 ± 13.4	10 ± 15.5
Hand-held & using	21	74 ± 13.6	9 ± 14.3	10 ± 14.2
Trousers back pocket	2	82 ± 19	6 ± 5.7	7 ± 6.3
Trousers front pocket	1	75 ± 0	7 ± 0.0	10 ± 0.0
Handbag	5	94 ± 9.6	14 ± 5.5	18 ± 6.8
Backpack	16	77 ± 7.9	5 ± 3.8	6 ± 4.7
Shirt pocket	1	94 ± 0.0	11 ± 0.0	13 ± 0.0

Table 3: Activity type recognition classification results on the dataset of [32]

	lay	stand	walk	run	cycle	stairs
lay	94.4	5.5	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1
stand	0.8	95.3	0.8	0.5	1.8	1.0
walk	0.0	1.1	86.4	0.1	0.6	11.8
run	0.0	3.3	0.4	94.3	0.3	1.7
cycle	0.5	7.6	3.5	0.7	83.6	4.0
stairs	0.1	3.0	12.8	2.0	1.6	80.5

Table 4: Evaluation of the visited-locations detection algorithm [33] on the SHL dataset.

Subject	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall	F1-score
1	8	0	1	1.00	0.89	0.94
2	15	2	4	0.88	0.79	0.83
3	13	2	3	0.87	0.81	0.84
sum	36	4	8	0.90	0.82	0.86

Table 5: Evaluation of the transportation-mode detection algorithm on the SHL dataset. Results are given per window.

	walk/run	bike	car	bus	train/subway
walk/run	2990	163	68	119	39
bike	138	1487	4	0	0
car	1	7	1690	962	293
bus	6	1	380	1087	320
train/subway	1	11	48	870	5039

this reason, we isolated the unique 6 subject that do not suffer from major sleep disorders and can be characterized as normal sleepers.

Recordings last for an average of 9.13 hours and contain one sleep recording of mean duration of 7.02 hours. Total time of interrupts during sleeping periods is 35 minutes as average, distributed in 16 distinct interrupts.

Our dataset consists of 29 recordings from 9 distinct subjects who are researchers working in BigO. Subjects are aged between 25 and 40 years old, normal sleepers without any sleep disorder. Six of them are male and three are female. We requested them to keep information of their activity throughout the recording sessions. The formulation of ground truth information is the following: Every subject had to divide the recording session in sequential time intervals, each being labeled as one of four possible states.

The four states are:

- Awake: subject wears her/his smartwatch and is not sleeping nor lying on her/his bed
- In Bed: subject wears her/his smartwatch and is lying on her/his bed
- Sleep: subject is sleeping
- No Wear: subject does not wear her/his smartwatch

Annotation of recording session follows three rules:

1. Every recording session starts with a “Recording Start” event and ends with a “Recording End” event. After the Recording Start event, subject enters the Awake state.
2. The sequence of events [In Bed, Sleep Start, Sleep End, Off Bed] describes a sleeping period. Inside time interval [Sleep Start, Sleep End] subject is in Sleep state.
3. The sequence of events: [No wear, Wear] represents a non-wearing period, in which subject is in No Wear state.

Recordings last for an average of 14.12 hours and the mean duration of sleeping period is 6.8 hours. Two recordings contain two distinct sleeping periods.

In order to evaluate the performance of the two methods we define the following metrics. Each recording contains one or more sleep sessions. Let denote as $X_i, i \in \{1, \dots, 29\}$ every recording and $X_i^j \in \{i, \dots\}$ the j -th sleep session of X_i recording. S_i is the number of sessions that recording X_i contains and \hat{S}_i the number of sessions that our algorithm predicted.

Our primary goal is predicting correctly the number of sleep sessions for each recording. We define the metric percentage of correct sleep sessions (CSS) as:

$$CSS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N 1, \text{ if } S_i = \hat{S}_i}{N} \quad (1)$$

CSS is crucial since all sleep indicators metrics depend on it.

Table 6: Evaluation of Sahe’s algorithm on the BigO and Newcastle datasets. We present the mean (μ), standard deviations (σ), and maximum (max) absolute error (in minutes) per indicator; we also present the correct sleep sessions (CSS) per dataset.

	BigO dataset			Newcastle dataset		
	μ	σ	max	μ	σ	max
GST	11.8	10.1	50.0	17.9	11.8	44.0
SS	9.3	10.4	43.6	18.7	19.7	57.6
SE	4.5	3.3	14.4	11.6	3.2	15.9
TTI	-	-	-	16.7	5.4	28.0
NI	-	-	-	9.9	5.6	19.0
NST	-	-	-	20.3	10.0	30.0
<i>CSS</i>	96.55%			100%		

If our algorithm is able to correctly detect most sleep sessions, we then define another set of metrics that evaluates sleep indicators. For each $X_i^j, i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, j \in \{1, \dots\}$ we define a set of variables:

- Sleep Start (SS_i^j) is the date-time in which sleep session j of subject i begins
- Sleep End (SE_i^j) is the date-time in which sleep session j of subject i ends
- Gross Sleep Time (GST_i^j) is the duration of sleep session j of subject i : $GST_i^j = SE_i^j - SS_i^j$
- Number of interrupts (NI_i^j) is the number of interrupts during sleep session j of subject i
- Total time of interrupts (TTI_i^j) is the aggregated duration of all interrupts during sleep session j of subject i
- Net Sleep Time (NST_i^j) is the duration of sleep session j of subject i , without the interrupts: $NST_i^j = GST_i^j - TTI_i^j$

Evaluation of above variables is accomplished by computing the absolute error (AE) in minutes, between prediction and ground truth for each recording.

On our BigO dataset, we evaluate metrics: CSS , $\mu(GST)$, $\mu(SS)$, and $\mu(SE)$ were μ is the mean absolute error in minutes. It is not feasible to validate algorithm’s performance on NI , TTI , and NST due to the absence of ground truth information on subject’s behavior throughout sleep session.

6 Real-world uses

An implementation of the proposed system was used in the context of the BigO project in 33 schools in Thessaloniki, Athens, Stockholm, Uppsala, and in two childhood obesity clinics in Athens and Dublin. The system was supported by a a number of front-end applications (portals), including a school portal, a clinical portal, as well as portal for policy makers [50]. A total of 3,700 children contributed data, leading to the collection of 7,499

days of accelerometry, 4,692 days of GPS, 169,316 meal pictures and 35,012 answers to mood questions. Further details about the deployment of the system can be found in [10,50,51]. In [50], the BigO system was used to understand the environment close to the school in Stockholm, Sweden and Thessaloniki, Greece. Results of [50] show that increased availability of food or physical-activity related places near to school affects the students behavior: students tend to eat more on food-related places if they are available close to their school, but also tend to have increased physical activity levels if there are more sports facilities available to them nearby.

As a public-health tool, BigO was used in three separate cases: (a) in Stockholm, Sweden, to understand eating-location preference (school vs. retail shops) in high-school populations, (b) in Thessaloniki, Greece, to compare consumption of processed and ultra-processed foods in two socioeconomically-distinct areas, and (c) in Stockholm, Sweden and in Larissa and Thessaloniki, Greece, to monitor longitudinal population-behavior change before and during the COVID-19 crisis. Ethical approval has been obtained in Sweden, Stockholm (DNR: 2016/598-31) and in AUTH, Thessaloniki, Greece (DNR: 132649/2017 and 104673/2018)

As a clinical tool, the system was used in a population of overweight and obese adolescents in the clinic for the Prevention and Management of Overweight and Obesity, Division of Endocrinology, Metabolism and Diabetes, First Department of Pediatrics, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Medical School, “Aghia Sophia” Children’s Hospital, Athens, Greece. The system was used to evaluate the correlation between BMI and behaviors measured by the BigO system, as well as the effect of the COVID outbreak and subsequent measures on the population behavior [52,53]. In particular, with the BigO system used as an intervention in a population of 251 obese or overweight children and adolescents, BMI decreased by 1.4% ($28.1kg/m^2$ vs. $27.6kg/m^2$, $p < 0.001$) in all subjects [52].

Additionally, in [54], the relation between fast eating and BMI was examined. In a Swedish population of 116 students, those with higher BMI also had faster eating rate ($+7.7g/min$ or $+27\%$, $p = 0.012$). And in a second population that included 748 Swedish and 1084 Greek high-school students, similar observations were made. The Ph.D. thesis of Peter Fagerberg [55] expanded on these results.

In [56], a population of 647 students in Greece and Sweden was analyzed with regards to their consumption of ultra-processed foods as well as fruits and vegetables, before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Analysis showed that consumption of ultra-processed foods decreased during the pandemic while consumption of fruits and vegetables increased.

Furthermore, a version of the proposed system was used by Eurostat in the NTTS-2019 Big Data hackathon [7]. More specifically, subjects from around Europe (personnel of European National Statistics Offices) used the system for approximately one month. This led to a dataset of 110 users where each user contributed data for 19 days. This

dataset was used in the hackathon for the development of use-cases for use of Big Data for official statistics. An example of results from participants using the collected data are available online [57], demonstrating results from the Polish Statistics Office (i.e., the winning team).

Finally, collaborating nutritionists are currently analyzing additional data of school populations for the areas of Thessaloniki, Greece and Stockholm, Sweden.

7 Conclusions

We have presented the architecture and main behavioral indicator extraction algorithms for a system that provides population-level measurements of behavior and environment indicators, focusing on obesity prevention at the policy level. The system relies on multi-modal information provided by smartphones and smartwatches to continuously extract behavioral indicators, which can then be aggregated at the individual and geographical area level. This aggregated information, along with self-reported data from questionnaires and pictures can then be used to support various applications in the school and clinical setting, as well as for policy decision support.

The proposed system uses several signal processing algorithms to extract indicators related to physical activity, types of locations visited, transportation modes used, and sleep. The algorithms have been adapted for use with modern smartphone and smartwatch devices, have been evaluated in datasets available in the literature and demonstrate satisfactory effectiveness.

From a technical implementation viewpoint, one important challenge involves the use of non-specialized equipment for data collection. Relying on the users’ personal devices for data collection places several limitations on the parameters related to the acquired signals. These have to do with constraints on the available signals imposed by the manufacturers, as well as limitations on “background” data collection, which require users to select complex application permissions in the smartphone’s OS. Overall, these obstacles can lead to missing data and/or low compliance, however they can be overcome with the collaboration of manufacturers in the future (e.g., to support systems for participatory science and for monitoring population health indicators).

Another challenge involves the collection and analysis of large volumes of sensor streams, as the number of concurrent users grows. The use of binary blobs in CassandraDB by our system proved effective and can be scalable, since CassandraDB can support distributed storage and, with the aid of Apache Spark, distributed processing. Other solutions (e.g., TimescaleDB, InfluxDB) have been recently proposed as mature implementations and they are worth evaluating. Moreover, it is worth emphasizing that in all cases it is preferable to process the raw sensor signals at the edge device, whenever possible, since this limits the amount of information stored centrally, leading to computational and privacy protection benefits.

The proposed system was used in studies for data collection by adults for the NTTS2019 Big Data Hackathon and by children and adolescents in the context of the BigO

project. It has demonstrated its effectiveness in these real-world setting, and shows that this participatory science approach can provide rich, passively collected information to help support large-scale studies on complex health challenges, such as obesity.

Finally, the proposed system is currently extended and adapted for the on-going, EU-funded REBECCA project [58, 59].

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